

Dongfang Special Entangled Schrödinger Wave Function of Hydrogen

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Abstract: Based on the missed exact solution special case of the newly discovered spherical harmonic partial differential equation, the analytical expression of the spherical harmonic function is regressed, and the wave function of the zero magnetic quantum number that overturns the traditional understanding of the Schrödinger equation theory for hydrogen atoms is briefly introduced. At the same time, the answer to the question of the existence and uniqueness of the probability density function definition based on the statistical interpretation of Born in quantum mechanics is clarified. Whether it is the inherent causal relationship hidden in the basic definition or the completely accurate solution of the wave equation, new conclusions clearly indicate that scientific theories described using partial differential equations, especially quantum mechanics, are facing significant changes, and all related theories will inevitably be rewritten after improving the theory of partial differential equations.

Keywords: Hydrogen atom; Schrödinger equation; Special entangled spherical harmonic function; Schrödinger wave function; Special entangled wave function; Probability density function.

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1 Introduction

The recently discovered special entangled spherical harmonic functions that are independent of the commonly described spherical harmonic functions^[1] indicate that the large numbers of exact solutions to certain partial differential equations are not described by established mathematical theories, indicating that various wave equations hide many missing solutions. Here, we briefly introduce two types of special entangled solutions with zero magnetic quantum numbers^[2] that have not been described in quantum mechanics. Their linear combination with traditional exact solutions forms a class of local complete set general solutions for the Schrödinger hydrogen equation. The results indicate that, in addition to the normalization condition, the specific form of the

exact solution to the Schrödinger hydrogen equation increases with the increase of energy levels, and the natural period condition, natural boundary condition, and normalization condition are not sufficient to form a definite solution problem with wave equations such as the Schrödinger hydrogen equation. However, the uncertainty of the special entangled wave function has no effect on the energy eigenvalue formula of the Schrödinger hydrogen equation. The three-dimensional contour lines of a special entangled wave function in the form of a real variable function are drawn by assigning undetermined coefficients, and the results intuitively and clearly demonstrate that there is no one-to-one correspondence between the wave function modulus and the wave function modulus square due to multivariate reasons. Therefore, the quantum mechanical definition that the probability density of particle appearance is the square of the wave function modulus is not supported by mathematical principles, and this conclusion also provides sufficient counterevidence for the uncertainty of any even power of the wave function.

2 The special complete set entangled wave function of hydrogen

The spiritual essence of quantum mechanics^[3,4] is that the non-completely exact solution of the wave equation that satisfies the definite solution condition leads to the quantized energy eigenvalues^[5-7], especially the energy eigenvalues of the Schrödinger equations^[8,9] for hydrogen atoms, which conform to the Bohr hydrogen atom quantized energy level formula^[10,11]. This energy level formula has been tested by experimental observations and becomes the standard for whether the wave equation is accepted, and determines the direction of the development of quantum mechanics^[12,13]. So, are there or how many different partial differential equations with exactly the same eigenvalue under the same definite solution conditions? This type of question breaks a single mindset, and the answer does not support the claim that quantum forces are mathematically precise and perfect.

Examine the completeness and rationality of exact solutions to wave equations. Let's first review the textbook exact solutions of the Schrödinger equation for hydrogen atoms, and then focus on the special entangled solutions of zero magnetic quantum numbers and their mathematical conclusions that have been overlooked. For the sake of simplicity and clarity, the Schrödinger wave equation theory for hydrogen atoms is summarized here as a lemma or theorem for definite solution problems and problem answers. This should develop into a fixed format for describing wave equation theory, in order to reduce the lengthy discourse that often amplifies misleading functions.

Problem (Schrödinger hydrogen atom): One of definite solution problems for the wave equation theory of hydrogen atoms with reduced mass μ , consisting of wave function bounded conditions, natural period conditions, normalization conditions, and Schrödinger equation,

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} -\frac{\hbar^2}{2\mu}\nabla^2\psi - \frac{\alpha\hbar c}{r}\psi = E\psi \\ \psi(r \rightarrow \infty) = 0, \psi(0 \leq r, 0 \leq \theta \leq \pi, 0 \leq \varphi \leq 2\pi) \neq \pm\infty \\ \psi(r, \theta + 2\pi, \varphi + 2\pi) = \psi(r, \theta, \varphi) \\ \int_{r=0}^{\infty} \left\{ \int_{\theta=0}^{\pi} \left[\int_{\varphi=0}^{2\pi} \psi(r, \theta, \varphi) \psi^*(r, \theta, \varphi) r^2 \sin\theta d\varphi \right] d\theta \right\} dr = 1 \end{array} \right. \quad (2.1)$$

Where α is the fine structure constant, c is the speed of light in vacuum, $\hbar = h/2\pi$ is the reduced Planck constant, E is the energy of the hydrogen atom, and ψ is the wave function. Operators in spherical coordinate systems

$$\nabla^2\psi = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial\theta^2} + \frac{\cos\theta}{\sin\theta} \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial\theta} + \frac{1}{\sin^2\theta} \frac{\partial^2\psi}{\partial\varphi^2} \right) \quad (2.2)$$

The standard textbook theory uses the separation of variables method to solve the Schrödinger equation mentioned above, and the results are usually represented as a combination of normalized direct product bounded functions. This left a deep impression on us: the integral constant of the bounded function solution of the Schrödinger equation seems to be completely determined by the normalization condition. According to differential equation theory, the special solution of a differential equation is a special case where the general solution satisfies the definite solution condition. To solve the Schrödinger wave equation, which essentially belongs to second-order linear partial differential equations, the general solution form with undetermined integral constants should still be given first. For the convenience of verification and new description, we now begin to regress the analytical form of the special function, and summarize the general solution of the traditional direct product function form of the Schrödinger equation for hydrogen atoms as the following lemma.

Lemma (traditional solution of Schrödinger equation): For magnetic quantum number m , orbital angular momentum quantum number l , and total quantum number n that satisfy conditions $|m| \leq l$ and $l < n$, a bounded wave function

$$\psi_{n,l}^{(m)}(r, \theta, \varphi) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} e^{-\frac{\alpha\mu cr}{\hbar}} r^l \left(1 + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{\eta=1}^{\nu} \frac{(\eta-n+l)}{\eta(\eta+2l+1)} \right) \left(\frac{2\alpha\mu c}{\hbar} \right)^{\nu} r^{\nu} \right) \\ \times \left(a_{n,l}^{(m)} \cos m\varphi + a_{n,l}^{(-m)} \sin m\varphi \right) \sin^m \theta \\ \times \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l+m-2)(2k+l+m-1)}{2k(2k-1)} \right) \cos^{2j} \theta \end{array} \right\}_{l-m=0,2,4,\dots} \\ + \left\{ \begin{array}{l} e^{-\frac{\alpha\mu cr}{\hbar}} r^l \left(1 + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{\eta=1}^{\nu} \frac{(\eta-n+l)}{\eta(\eta+2l+1)} \right) \left(\frac{2\alpha\mu c}{\hbar} \right)^{\nu} r^{\nu} \right) \\ \times \left(b_{n,l}^{(m)} \cos m\varphi + b_{n,l}^{(-m)} \sin m\varphi \right) \sin^m \theta \\ \times \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l+m-1)(2k+l+m)}{(2k+1)2k} \right) \cos^{2j+1} \theta \end{array} \right\}_{l-m=1,3,5,\dots} \end{array} \right\} \quad (2.3)$$

with two undetermined coefficients $a_{n,l}^{(m)}$ and $a_{n,l}^{(-m)}$ or $b_{n,l}^{(m)}$ and $b_{n,l}^{(-m)}$ satisfies the natural periodic condition $\psi(r, \theta + 2\pi, \varphi + 2\pi) = \psi(r, \theta, \varphi)$. It is one of the exact solutions to the steady-state Schrödinger equation

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\cos \theta}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{\sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \varphi^2} \right) + \left(\frac{2\alpha\mu c}{\hbar r} + \frac{2\mu E}{\hbar^2} \right) \psi = 0 \quad (2.4)$$

with an energy eigenvalue of

$$E = -\frac{\mu\alpha^2 c^2}{2n^2}, \quad (n = 1, 2, 3, \dots) \quad (2.5)$$

The standardized form of the traditional direct product function solution to the Schrödinger equation for hydrogen atoms mentioned above also has multiple undetermined coefficients, which cannot be determined using normalization conditions. But the standard textbook theory provides the normalization coefficient of the wave function. This is one of the hidden issues in the Schrödinger theory of hydrogen atoms, which is difficult to pay attention to due to its technical description. More importantly, due to serious flaws in the theory of partial differential equations,

boundary problems of the same partial differential equation often have a large number of missing solutions. There are two types of entangled function solutions for spherical harmonic partial differential equations with zero magnetic quantum numbers that have not been discovered in history. Any new spherical harmonic function will inevitably seriously affect the established Schrödinger wave equation theory.

When the magnetic quantum number is $m = 0$, the traditional solution of the Schrödinger equation degenerates into a binary function about r and θ , no longer containing the angle ϕ . This seemingly rigorous mathematical inference is actually not true. Replacing the cosine function $\cos \theta$ in the direct product function (2.3) with $\sin \phi \sin \theta$ and $\cos \phi \sin \theta$ respectively, the two types of special entangled wave functions obtained satisfy the Schrödinger equation for hydrogen atoms. According to the theory of differential equations, the linear combination of the traditional solution (2.3) and the two types of entangled wave functions obtained by substitution is the local general solution of the Schrödinger equation, known as the special complete set entangled Schrödinger wave function of hydrogen atoms. The lemma of traditional theory has been extended and summarized as the following theorem.

Theorem (Schrödinger special entangled wave function): Let the magnetic quantum number $m = 0$, for the orbital angular momentum quantum number l and total quantum number n that satisfy the condition $l < n$, with no less than $3n-2$ mutually independent undetermined coefficients $a_{n,l}$, $c_{n,l}$, and $f_{n,l}$ (or $b_{n,l}$, $d_{n,l}$, and $g_{n,l}$), the special complete set entangled wave function

$$\psi_n^{(0)}(r, \theta, \varphi) = \sum_{l=0}^{n-1} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left[e^{-\frac{\alpha\mu cr}{\hbar}} r^l \left(1 + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{\eta=1}^{\nu} \frac{(\eta-n+l)}{\eta(\eta+2l+1)} \right) \left(\frac{2\alpha\mu c}{\hbar} \right)^{\nu} r^{\nu} \right) \right. \\ \left. \times \left[\begin{array}{l} a_{n,l} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-2)(2k+l-1)}{2k(2k-1)} \right) \cos^{2j}\theta \\ + c_{n,l} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-2)(2k+l-1)}{2k(2k-1)} \right) (\sin \varphi \sin \theta)^{2j} \\ + f_{n,l} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-2)(2k+l-1)}{2k(2k-1)} \right) (\cos \varphi \sin \theta)^{2j} \end{array} \right] \right. \\ \left. \right\}_{l=0, 2, 4, \dots} \\ + \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left[e^{-\frac{\alpha\mu cr}{\hbar}} r^l \left(1 + \sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{\eta=1}^{\nu} \frac{(\eta-n+l)}{\eta(\eta+2l+1)} \right) \left(\frac{2\alpha\mu c}{\hbar} \right)^{\nu} r^{\nu} \right) \right. \\ \left. \times \left[\begin{array}{l} b_{n,l} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-1)(2k+l)}{(2k+1)2k} \right) \cos^{2j+1}\theta \\ + d_{n,l} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-1)(2k+l)}{(2k+1)2k} \right) (\sin \varphi \sin \theta)^{2j+1} \\ + g_{n,l} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-1)(2k+l)}{(2k+1)2k} \right) (\cos \varphi \sin \theta)^{2j+1} \end{array} \right] \right. \\ \left. \right\}_{l=1, 3, 5, \dots} \end{array} \right. \quad (2.6)$$

satisfies the steady-state Schrödinger equation

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial \Upsilon}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Upsilon}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\cos \theta}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial \Upsilon}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{\sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2 \Upsilon}{\partial \phi^2} \right) + \left(\frac{2\alpha\mu c}{\hbar r} + \frac{2\mu E}{\hbar^2} \right) \Upsilon = 0 \quad (2.7)$$

with energy eigenvalues

$$E = -\frac{\mu\alpha^2 c^2}{2n^2}, \quad (n = 1, 2, 3, \dots)$$

The proof of the theorem is divided into the radial function section and the angular function section. The radial function section can be found in the standard textbook theory. The proof process for the two types of entangled spherical harmonic functions that appear in the angular function section is only a simple but tedious calculation, written in the form of a mathematical article. For any relatively small quantum number that satisfies the agreed conditions in the theorem, the correctness of the theorem can be verified using a computer.

Exploring the essence of quantum mechanics and attempting to mathematically prove certain hypothetical principles of quantum mechanics, it can be found that the fine structure constant derived from Planck's constant is not a true constant. The two should be renamed as Planck parameters and fine structure parameters respectively. It is strongly recommended that experimental physicists accurately measure the distribution of fine structural parameters or Planck parameters.

The entangled wave function for the special case of magnetic quantum number $m = 0$ is very convenient for exploring the applicability of the normalization conditions of the wave function and whether the probability density definition based on the wave function is objective. By setting $n = 1, 2, 3, 4,$ and $5,$ and using (2.6) to calculate the first five complete sets of special entangled wave functions for hydrogen atoms with magnetic quantum number $m = 0,$ we can obtain several specific forms with increasing undetermined coefficients. These results clearly state the conclusions that have been overlooked throughout history, except for the ground state case, the multiple undetermined coefficients of the solution to any other case of the hydrogen Schrödinger equation cannot be determined, and therefore the specific form of the wave function cannot be determined. The normalization coefficients of wave functions given in history are pseudo coefficients disguised under descriptive techniques, rather than necessarily causal conclusions.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \psi_1^{(0)} &= \beta_{1,0} e^{-\frac{c\alpha\mu}{\hbar} r} \\
 \psi_2^{(0)} &= e^{-\frac{c\alpha\mu}{2\hbar} r} \left[\beta_{2,0} \left(1 - \frac{c\alpha\mu r}{2\hbar} \right) + b_{2,1} r \cos \theta + r \sin \theta (d_{2,1} \sin \varphi + g_{2,1} \cos \varphi) \right] \\
 \psi_3^{(0)} &= e^{-\frac{c\alpha\mu}{3\hbar} r} \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\beta_{3,0} \left(1 + \frac{2c^2\alpha^2\mu^2 r^2}{27\hbar^2} - \frac{2c\alpha\mu r}{3\hbar} \right) \\ &+ r^2 \left[a_{3,2} (1 - 3\cos^2 \theta) + c_{3,2} (1 - 3\sin^2 \theta \sin^2 \varphi) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + f_{3,2} (1 - 3\cos^2 \varphi \sin^2 \theta) \right] \\ &+ \left(r - \frac{c\alpha\mu r^2}{6\hbar} \right) [b_{3,1} \cos \theta + \sin \theta (d_{3,1} \sin \varphi + g_{3,1} \cos \varphi)] \end{aligned} \right\} \\
 \psi_4^{(0)} &= e^{-\frac{c\alpha\mu}{4\hbar} r} \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\beta_{4,0} \left(1 - \frac{c^3\alpha^3\mu^3 r^3}{192\hbar^3} + \frac{c^2\alpha^2\mu^2 r^2}{8\hbar^2} - \frac{3c\alpha\mu r}{4\hbar} \right) \\ &+ \left(r^2 - \frac{c\alpha\mu r^3}{12\hbar} \right) \left[a_{4,2} (1 - 3\cos^2 \theta) + c_{4,2} (1 - 3\sin^2 \theta \sin^2 \varphi) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + f_{4,2} (1 - 3\cos^2 \varphi \sin^2 \theta) \right] \\ &+ \frac{r (c^2\alpha^2\mu^2 r^2 - 20c\alpha\mu\hbar r + 80\hbar^2)}{80\hbar^2} \\ &\quad \times [b_{4,1} \cos \theta + \sin \theta (d_{4,1} \sin \varphi + g_{4,1} \cos \varphi)] \\ &- \frac{1}{3} r^3 \left\{ \begin{aligned} &b_{4,3} \cos \theta (5\cos^2 \theta - 3) \\ &+ \sin \theta \left[d_{4,3} \sin \varphi (5\sin^2 \theta \sin^2 \varphi - 3) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + g_{4,3} \cos \varphi (5\cos^2 \varphi \sin^2 \theta - 3) \right] \end{aligned} \right\} \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{2.8}
 \end{aligned}$$

Among them, $\beta_{n,0}$ is the reduced undetermined coefficient, also known as the undetermined

integral constant.

The statistical interpretation of wave functions enables them to be given normalization conditions, thus only determining the integral constant of the ground state wave function. The normalization coefficients of other wave functions are not the true results of normalization, but are masked by the smoothness of specific descriptions. The general form of normalization conditions is

$$\int_0^{\infty} \left(\int_0^{\pi} \left(\int_0^{2\pi} \psi^2 d\varphi \right) \sin \theta d\theta \right) r^2 dr = 1 \quad (2.9)$$

Among the several complete set special entangled Schrödinger wave functions listed in (2.8), only the total quantum number $n = 1$, so the undetermined coefficient $\beta_{1,0}$ of the ground state wave function with orbital angular momentum quantum number $l = 0$ is unique and can be determined by normalization conditions. The ground state wave function has specific forms,

$$\psi_1^{(0)} = \sqrt{\frac{c^3 \Lambda^3 \mu^3}{\pi \hbar^3}} e^{-\frac{c\alpha\mu}{\hbar} r} \quad (2.10)$$

But the wave function with a total quantum number $n > 1$ has $3n - 2$ independent undetermined coefficients, and the normalization condition can only provide the relationship that these undetermined coefficients satisfy, but cannot determine the multiple independent undetermined coefficients. According to the so-called normalization condition, the relationship equations for the undetermined coefficients of the entangled wave function of a complete set with $n = 2, 3, 4$, respectively, are,

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{8\pi\hbar^3 (4\hbar^2 (b_{2,1}^2 + d_{2,1}^2 + g_{2,1}^2) + \alpha^2 \mu^2 c^2 \beta_{2,0}^2)}{c^5 \alpha^5 \mu^5} = 1 \\ & \frac{27\pi\hbar^3}{8\alpha^7 \mu^7 c^7} \left\{ 27\hbar^2 \left[\begin{aligned} & 432\hbar^2 \left(\begin{aligned} & a_{3,2}^2 + c_{3,2}^2 - c_{3,2} f_{3,2} \\ & + f_{3,2}^2 - a_{3,2} (c_{3,2} + f_{3,2}) \end{aligned} \right) \\ & + \alpha^2 \mu^2 c^2 (b_{3,1}^2 + d_{3,1}^2 + g_{3,1}^2) \end{aligned} \right] + 8\alpha^4 \mu^4 c^4 \beta_{3,0}^2 \right\} = 1 \\ & \frac{125\pi\hbar^3}{56c^{11} \alpha^{11} \mu^{11}} \left\{ \begin{aligned} & 50000c^4 \alpha^4 \mu^4 \hbar^4 a_{5,2}^2 + 122500000000\hbar^8 a_{5,4}^2 \\ & - 50000c^4 \alpha^4 \mu^4 \hbar^4 a_{5,2} (c_{5,2} + f_{5,2}) \\ & + 91875000000\hbar^8 a_{5,4} (c_{5,4} + f_{5,4}) \\ & + 25\hbar^2 (7c^6 \alpha^6 \mu^6 b_{5,1}^2 + 109375c^2 \alpha^2 \mu^2 \hbar^4 b_{5,3}^2 \\ & + 2000c^4 \alpha^4 \mu^4 \hbar^2 c_{5,2}^2 + 49000000000\hbar^6 c_{5,4}^2 \\ & + 7c^6 \alpha^6 \mu^6 d_{5,1}^2 + 109375c^2 \alpha^2 \mu^2 \hbar^4 d_{5,3}^2 \\ & - 2000c^4 \alpha^4 \mu^4 \hbar^2 c_{5,2} f_{5,2} + 2000c^4 \alpha^4 \mu^4 \hbar^2 f_{5,2}^2 \\ & + 3675000000\hbar^6 c_{5,4} f_{5,4} + 4900000000\hbar^6 f_{5,4}^2 \\ & + 7c^6 \alpha^6 \mu^6 g_{5,1}^2 + 109375c^2 \alpha^2 \mu^2 \hbar^4 g_{5,3}^2) + 56c^8 \alpha^8 \mu^8 \beta_{5,0}^2 \end{aligned} \right\} = 1 \end{aligned} \quad (2.11)$$

Within the framework of quantum mechanics, which is determined by the statistical interpretation of wave functions, it is impossible to supplement the definite solution conditions that increase with the total quantum number to determine these undetermined coefficients and thus determine the specific form of the wave function. This fact provides a new conclusion for the Schrödinger wave equation theory in quantum mechanics.

Inference 1: When the total quantum number is n , there are $3n - 2$ undetermined integral constants for the entangled eigensolutions of the complete set of the Schrödinger equation for hydrogen atoms, and the specific form of the wave function cannot be determined. In short, there is no specific functional solution to the Schrödinger equation for hydrogen atoms in the statistical sense of wave functions.

3 Problem of existence and uniqueness of probability density function

The abstract Born statistical interpretation of wave function^[14] is actually very vague, and the definition of probability density function has not been strictly proven. And the distortion from the image of the modulus of the wave function to the image of the square of the modulus of the redefined wave function representing probability density is a fatal flaw and one of the reasons why the mathematical essence of quantum mechanics has always been difficult to reveal. Starting from the physical meaning of probability density, derive the probability density function of interacting microscopic particles appearing at any position in space in certain models, and then clarify the relationship between this probability density function and the Schrödinger equation, which is the best solution to solve the difficulties of quantum mechanics. The fact we are going to reveal is that the wave function satisfying the Schrödinger equation is actually uncertain and can only have a relatively abstract form. Specifically, except for the ground state wave function which can have a definite form by determining the integral constant through normalization conditions, all wave functions of other energy levels do not have corresponding definite solution conditions to determine the integral constant and obtain a specific form.

The complete set special entangled wave function (2.3) is a representative of the missed solution of the Schrödinger equation for hydrogen atoms, indicating the serious mathematical shortcomings of quantum mechanics wave equation theory. Now, using the complete set special entangled wave function further illustrates the logical problems hidden in the definition of probability density in the context of Born's statistical interpretation. It cannot be proven scientifically that quantum mechanics uses the wave function modulus squared to represent the probability density of particles appearing in the space. The initial definition of the probability density function may be based on the selection of three features: 1) The square of the modulus function and the modulus function are both positive definite functions; 2) The square of the modular function has the same zero and extreme points as the modular function; 3) The square of the modulus function is more convenient in calculation than the modulus function. However, these features only belong to univariate functions, while multivariate functions do not have these features. This is one of the major oversights in defining the probability density function. Another major oversight is that any even power of a modular function is a positive definite function, and the zero and extreme points of any even power of a univariate modular function remain unchanged. If the reason for defining probability density in quantum mechanics is valid, then it cannot be ruled out to define a density function for any positive integer k ,

$$\rho(r, \theta, \phi) = |\psi(r, \theta, \phi)|^{2k} \quad (3.1)$$

However, there is no logical basis to prove that $k = 1$ is a unique value. The logical power of counter evidence is beyond doubt.

In mathematics, functions can be defined with specific mathematical meanings. But in physics, functions are used to describe natural laws and cannot be defined based on certain mathematical characteristics. When it is impossible to prove the appropriateness of the definition of the probability density function through experimental observation, a sufficient number of similar definitions lead to mutual negation of the uncertainty of the spatial distribution of physical quantities described by the function, thus negating the initial narrow definition. The normalization condition can be applied to any bounded function, but it may not necessarily be the standard for describing natural laws. Taking $\psi_3^{(0)}$ in equation (2.8) as an example, taking all constants as one unit and all undetermined coefficients as 1, the specific form of the agreed wave function is:

$$\psi_3^{(0)} = e^{-r/3} \left\{ 1 - \frac{2r}{3} + \frac{2r^2}{27} - \left(\frac{r}{6} - 1 \right) r [\cos \theta + \sin \theta (\cos \phi + \sin \phi)] \right\} \quad (3.2)$$

Table 3D contour lines of the modulus and modulus square of the special entangled Schrödinger wave function

Radial interval	$0 \leq r \leq 10$	$0 \leq r \leq 25$
Wave function modulus		
Wave function modulus squared		

Draw the three-dimensional contour lines of the modulus and its square of the wave function (3.2), and the image is listed in the table. The contour lines intuitively and clearly indicate that there is a significant difference in the spatial distribution of the two multivariate functions, without a one-to-one correspondence. This leads to another new conclusion about the Schrödinger wave equation theory in quantum mechanics.

Inference 2: Only any even power of a univariate wave function module corresponds one-to-one with zero and extreme points of the same function module. The distribution of even power functions of multivariate wave function modules is related to even power, and there is no one-to-one correspondence between zero and extreme points. It cannot be proven that the square of the wave function module is the only choice to define the probability density function. The statistical interpretation of quantum mechanics lacks sufficient logic and experimental basis, and is full of irreconcilable contradictions.

4 Conclusions

This paper presents a special case of various missed exact solutions to the Schrödinger equation. Based on the basic principles of differential equation theory, the abstract function form of the special general solution of the complete set of zero magnetic quantum numbers for the Schrödinger equation is clarified. The reason why the normalization condition cannot determine the specific solution of the wave equation that is essentially a second-order linear partial differential equation is

explained, and the non objectivity and hidden logical difficulties of the definition of the probability density function in the statistical sense of the wave function are analyzed. The wave function of hydrogen atoms is a microcosm of quantum mechanics theory. Even as a special case of the large number of solutions missing from the Schrödinger equation for hydrogen atoms, the special entangled wave function is sufficient to demonstrate the urgency of improving the theory of quantum mechanical wave equations. The solutions of the Schrödinger equation for other models are similar, but there are also irreversible conclusions such as the uncertainty of the complete set wave function and the distortion of the shape from the wave function mode to the wave function mode square, resulting in the loss of probability density significance of the wave function mode square. The confidence level of quantum mechanics wave equation theory is very low. All theories based on wave equations must be rewritten after improving the theory of partial differential equations.

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Notes: The lemmas, theorems, examples, and conclusions in the paper have all been verified by the computational software Wolfram Mathematica, so the proof process of the theorem is not written in the paper. For lengthy equations, formatting errors may occur during the process of writing Mathematica code. It is necessary to split the equations into several parts and process them separately, and then combine them to perform operations.

• **PS1: What is the significance of non renowned scientists submitting outstanding scientific contributions to renowned journals?**

This is a brief edition of the groundbreaking paper “[Dongfang Special Entangled Solution of Schrödinger Hydrogen Equation](#)” that subverts the exact solution of the hydrogen atom Schrödinger equation. The briefing version has added new scientific ideas on the basis of the detailed version.

The paper was submitted to Nature and Physical Review Letters respectively, and the results, like other groundbreaking papers previously submitted to Chinese scientific journals such as “SCIENCE CHINA Mathematics”, “SCIENCE CHINA Physics, Mechanics & Astronomy, SCPMA”, “Science Bulletin”, “Chinese Physics C”, “Acta Physica Sinica”, “Acta Mathematica Sinica, Chinese Series”, etc., once again revealed to those who pursue scientific truth the reality of the scientific community: famous journals have long been controlled by ignorant, immoral, and despicable people, widely used to promote lies under the banner of science to maximize personal interests, without promoting any groundbreaking discoveries that

are irrelevant to their personal or group interests. The outstanding scientific contributions of unknown scientists will only be stifled and plagiarized there. In the era of capital, many scientists, editors of academic journals, and peer reviewers do not have a true scientific belief, and they have even lost their humanity. They only pursue fame and fortune and resort to any means necessary.

Think about how many great discoveries have been humiliated, ravaged, and stifled by renowned scientific journals! However, the proceeds of theft or plagiarism can only be fragmented works and cannot be systematic scientific ideas. For nearly a century, great discoverers who remained silent have been almost invariably stifled or plagiarized by ignorant and unethical editors and peer reviewers of renowned scientific journals, yet scientific theories have never made substantial progress as a result. For example, the simple problem of the mathematical essence of quantum mechanics has yet to be solved by the powerful scientific community that has seized power. This is the fundamental reason why scientific theories have been stuck in a dirty quagmire for 100 years. Famous scientific journals influence the direction of scientific development, leading to a plethora of lies in the physics community and continuing to move in the wrong direction.

The Chinese theoretical physics professors and academicians I have been in contact with do not have any pioneering research abilities, but they try their best to steal others' breakthrough research results. Do international scientists often mock the Chinese theoretical physics community? In history, Chinese people have not made any breakthrough contributions to physics theory that can be included in textbooks, but there are too many Chinese people who constantly promote themselves as excellent theoretical physicists throughout the year. And the breakthrough research achievements that will truly impact the future scientific world are stifled. Now I have to give up my plan to write 100 breakthrough papers in mathematics and physics. This is not only pleasing to the Chinese official theoretical physics community constructed by extremely foolish people, because they can continue to enjoy the vanity of so-called theoretical physics academicians and theoretical physicists; This is also pleasing to the theoretical physics community in Europe and America, because a great scientist who could have been on par with the great Newton in the future - the true master of theoretical physics in China - was silently and completely eliminated by the Chinese themselves.

People who pursue truth should now understand a simple truth: only when the global scientific community establishes a sound system, so that famous scientific journals are no longer controlled by ignorant, immoral, and despicable people, can science usher in a new era of brilliance.

• **PS2: What would happen if an unknown scientist submits groundbreaking scientific contributions to Nature?**

Cover Letter

Beijing time: June 11, 2024 21:52 (Tuesday)

Dear Editors,

I am submitting this letter to your journal, which foreshadows significant changes in natural science theory and experimental testing due to the discovery of serious flaws in partial differential equation theory. It looks forward to promoting the rapid development of natural science theory in the right direction.

As an unknown discoverer from China, submitting groundbreaking papers to any journal is an insult to oneself. Whether in the past, present, or future, such great discoveries have been or are destined to be stifled. Nevertheless, in response to readers' doubts, I still often submit papers introducing major discoveries to world-renowned journals, perhaps this is the last time. The expectation of unexpected luck is not a rational behavior, and it is meaningful to make more readers aware of the scientific reality that individuals cannot change.

May all good luck come to you. Everything goes smoothly.

Thank you!

Best wishes,

X. D. Dongfang

†**Receipt of Nature manuscript 2024-06-11880**

Beijing time: June 11, 2024 21:53 (Tuesday)

Please ensure you delete the link to your author home page in this e-mail if you wish to forward it to your coauthors.

Dear Professor Dongfang,

Thank you for submitting your manuscript, "Dongfang Special Schrödinger Wave Function for Hydrogen". Your submission has been assigned the following tracking number: 2024-06-11880. We ask that you use this tracking number in any communication.

This e-mail simply acknowledges receipt of your submission. It does not imply that the paper will be sent out for formal review. Should the editors decide for editorial reasons that the paper is unsuitable for publication in Nature, you will be informed as soon as possible.

If an editor decides to send your manuscript for external review, they will first contact you and ask you to complete an Editorial Policy Checklist that verifies compliance with all required editorial policies. Please note that we will not be able to send your manuscript out to review until we have received the completed form, which will be made available to the reviewers. More information about our editorial policies, including a flattened version of this form, can be found at <https://www.nature.com/authors/policies/availability.html>.

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We will be in touch once a decision has been made.

Yours sincerely,

Manuscript Administration, Nature

www.nature.com/nature

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†NATURE: Your submission to Nature

Beijing time: June 12, 2024 18:28 (Wednesday)

Dear Professor Dongfang,

Thank you for submitting your manuscript to Nature, which we are regretfully unable to offer to publish.

It is Nature's policy to return a substantial proportion of manuscripts without sending them to referees, so that they may be sent elsewhere without delay. Decisions of this kind are made by the editorial staff when it appears that papers are unlikely to succeed in the competition for limited space.

In the present case, while your findings may well prove stimulating to others' thinking about such questions, we are unable to conclude that the work provides the sort of firm advance in general understanding that would warrant publication in Nature. We therefore feel that the paper would find a more suitable outlet in a specialist journal.

We are sorry that we cannot respond more positively on this occasion but hope that you will rapidly receive a more favourable response elsewhere.

Yours sincerely,

Manuscript Administration, Nature

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Author's inquiry letter

Beijing time: June 18, 2024 00:58 (Tuesday)

Dear Editor,

I don't understand why there is no submission record for this groundbreaking paper manuscript in the Nature system. Although the editor believes that they do not have professional knowledge and suggests submitting the manuscript to a professional magazine, the record of submission should be kept in the Nature system. Clicking on the link only displays information about previously rejected manuscripts. Please explain. Thank you!

X. D. Dongang

†Nature's automatic reply

Beijing time: June 18, 2024 00:58 (Tuesday)

Thank you for contacting Nature. This inbox is monitored on weekdays during UK and New York office hours only. We will try to respond to your email with 48 hours. Thank you for your patience. Kind regards, Nature Editorial Administration Team.

• PS3: What will be the outcome of submitting outstanding scientific contributions from unknown scientists to Physical Review Letters?

Cover Letter

Dear Editor,

This paper titled "Dongfang Special Entangled Schrödinger Wave Function of Hydrogen" provides a special case of a large number of missing solutions to the hydrogen atom Schrödinger equation that has never appeared in history. It is hoped that it can quickly spread to the scientific community to promote the revision and improvement of scientific theory.

The theory of partial differential equations has serious flaws, and the scientific theories described by partial differential equations, especially the wave equation theory in quantum mechanics, are not entirely correct. Natural science theory is facing a huge revolution.

There is an important experimental suggestion after equation (7). Expect the results of precise experiments to confirm strict logical deductions rather than hypotheses that meet expectations.

If the journal does not accept this paper, please forward it to senior scientists for research on similar issues and publication.

Thank you.

Sincerely,

X. D. Dongfang

Editorial Acknowledgment LT19318 Dongfang

Beijing time: June 26, 2024 at 01:26 (Wednesday)

Re: LT19318

Dongfang special entangled Schrodinger wave function of hydrogen

by X. D. Dongfang

Dear Dr. Doongfang,

The editors acknowledge receipt of this manuscript on 23 June 2024 and are considering it as a Letter in Physical Review Letters.

It has been indicated at submission that you be designated as the corresponding author for this manuscript.

If you already have an APS journal account, you will be able to access this submission by visiting <https://authors.aps.org/Submissions> and logging in with your journal account credentials. Alternatively, you can create one at <https://journals.aps.org/signup> if you do not have an account yet.

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Yours sincerely,

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Code number: LT19318

Journal: Physical Review Letters Letter

Received: 23 June 2024

Section: Quantum Information, Science, and Technology

Preprint number:

(x) Please supply the eprint archive number, if available.

PhySH Concepts:

Nonrelativistic wave equations (Primary)|Quantum correlations in quantum information|Quantum correlations, foundations & formalism|Quantum field theory (low energy)|Quantum foundations|Relativistic wave equations

Title: Dongfang special entangled Schrödinger wave function of hydrogen

Collaboration:

1 Author(s):

X. D. Dongfang

Your manuscript LT19318 Dongfang
Beijing time: July 8th, 2024 23:17 (Monday)

Re: LT19318

**Dongfang special entangled Schrodinger wave function of hydrogen
by X. D. Dongfang**

Dear Dr. Dongfang,

Your manuscript has been considered. We regret to inform you that we have concluded that it is not suitable for publication in Physical Review Letters.

Yours sincerely,

Stojan Rebic, Ph.D.

Senior Associate Editor

Physical Review Letters

Email: prl@aps.org

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